

The Connection between Sleep Deprivation and Being Overweight

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Abstract

The importance of sleep in maintaining good health and well-being throughout one's life can hardly be overstated. It is well established that sleep has an effect on a person's physical and emotional health by bringing about significant alterations in their biological and psychosocial states.

Few studies have looked at the relationship between the amount of sleep an individual gets and their body composition using a sample of young adults that is representative of the general population. When it comes to this age group, primary prevention is the most important factor to consider. As part of our research, we made the decision to look into the relationship between the amount of time spent sleeping and the composition of the body, as well as to make any applicable recommendations regarding changes in lifestyle.

Materials and Methods: The purpose of the research that was conducted on 100 healthy young adults between the ages of 18 and 25 using the Bodystat Quadscan 4000 was to investigate the effect that sleep has on body composition after receiving ethical clearance from an institutional ethical committee.

Results: The research concluded that there were statistically significant differences in both anthropometric and body composition parameters.

Conclusion: The amount of time spent sleeping plays a significant part in determining changes in body composition.

Keywords: Sleep deprivation; obesity; bioelectric impedance analyzer.

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Introduction

Obesity and sleep deprivation are two epidemics that have not only afflicted the developed nations, but also, as a result of rapid industrialization, the developing nations as well. Both of these problems have arisen as a direct result of our increasingly industrialised world. The survey that was carried out in the United States showed that over the course of the past 50 years, self-reported duration of sleep has decreased by between 1.5 and 2 hours, and the possible cause could be shifting lifestyle trends. [1,2] Research on

sleep has been conducted quite frequently in the course of looking for the underlying cause of modifiable risk factors. A sufficient amount of sleep is absolutely necessary for the healthy operation of the central nervous system. [3,4] Coronary artery disease, atherosclerosis, hypertension, obesity, and diabetes mellitus have all been linked to a lack of sleep. [5,6] Obesity has also been linked to a lack of sleep. [7] As was previously stated, not getting enough sleep can have negative effects on one's health and can also affect

one's body mass index. Even though other factors such as physical activity, diet, and heredity also contribute toward body composition, sleep is one of the most important factors in determining body composition. [8-14] The individual who sleeps more is in the category where primary prevention is the most important factor, according to the findings of certain cross-sectional research. As part of our research, we came to the conclusion that we should look into the relationship between the amount of time spent sleeping and one's body composition, as well as provide recommendations for any necessary changes to one's way of life.

Materials and Methods

This study was carried out in June 2022 to October 2022 after receiving approval on an ethical level from the institutional ethical committee. From the population of CIMS, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh a total of 62 young adults between the ages of 18 and 25 who were in good health were chosen at random. Before beginning the study, informed written consent was obtained from the people who were being studied. Subjects were not included in the study if they had any impairments related to the cardiovascular system, the nervous system, the endocrine system, the liver, or their kidneys. In addition, participants who used tobacco, sleeping pills, alcoholic beverages, or any other kind of recreational drug were excluded from the study. A condensed version of the procedure was discussed with the participants. They were instructed to refrain from consuming any tea, coffee, or food one hour prior to the recording. On the day of the recording, they were instructed to check in at the department's research lab between the hours of 9:00 and 11:00 in the morning. On the day of the exam, they were instructed to refrain from strenuous physical activity. The question concerning the amount of time spent sleeping, measured in hours, was posed to the young adults who took part in the research project over the course of the previous twelve

months. A questionnaire [15] was used to evaluate the length of sleep and the quality of sleep, and both of these findings have been published. [16] A calculation was made to determine the typical amount of time spent sleeping on weekdays, weekends, and holidays. The following calculation was used to determine the total time: (weekday duration 5/7) + (weekend duration 2/7). The total amount of time spent sleeping at night accounted for both nighttime sleep and daytime sleep. Inadequate sleep duration at night (IASDN) was defined as sleep duration of less than seven hours, while adequate sleep duration at night was defined as seven hours or more.

On an electronic weighing machine, body weight (W_t) was measured while the subject was barefoot and wearing only the barest minimum of clothing. The height was determined by standing barefoot while using a stadiometer to take the measurement. Measurements were taken of the hip circumference (HC) and the waist circumference (WC).

Procedure for Recording

Participants were instructed to assume a supine position and wait there. After lying down for no more than five minutes, each reading was taken. The multifrequency bioelectrical impedance analyzer known as Bodystat QuadScan 4000 was used to perform the fluid assessment and body composition analysis. The following parameters were evaluated: body mass index (BMI), waist-hip ratio (WHR), total body water (TBW), lean body mass (LBM), and body fat mass (FM). Graph Pad InStat, version 3.1, running on 32 bits of Windows was used to perform the statistical analysis on the collected data.

Results

The IASDN group had a total of 50 participants, while the ASDN group had a total of 50 participants. On the basis of anthropometric parameters, both groups displayed a statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$) as shown in [Table 1].

The difference between the two groups was extremely significant ($P = 0.000$), with the IASDN group having a mean body weight of 70 Kg and the ASDN group having a mean body weight of 60 Kg. It was found that the WC was significantly higher in the IASDN group (85 cm) compared to the ASDN group (80 cm), and this difference had a significance level of *** ($P = 0.000$). HC was significantly lower in the ASDN group, with values of 90 cm, compared to significantly higher values in the IASDN group, which were WC= 95 cm. This difference was statistically significant ($P = 0.009$).

WHR, a predictor for cardiovascular and metabolic risk, also showed a significantly higher value in IASDN, coming in at 0.90 compared to 0.80 in ASDN. This difference was statistically significant. The significance of the WHR's 0.000 p value,

which can be expressed as ***, is as follows: In the IASDN group, the assessment of body composition parameters revealed significantly elevated levels that were statistically significant. There was a statistically significant difference in the BMI between the two groups, with the IASDN group having a value of 20 kg/m² and the ASDN group having a value of 21 kg/m² ($P = 0.020$). Inadequate sleep duration was associated with a greater amount of body fat as compared to adequate sleep duration (Body fat in IASDN = 8kg and ASDN = 6.5 kg, $P = 0.20$); adequate sleep duration was associated with a lower amount of body fat.

IASDN patients also had significantly increased LBM and TBW, which was a finding that was statistically significant [Table 2].

Table 1: Anthropometric and body composition parameters in subjects of both groups

Parameters	IASDN(n=50)	ASDN(n=50)	P value
Bodyweight(kg)	70 ±10.22	60.11±9.88	P<0.001
WC (cm)	85.11±9.29	80.1±7.45	P<0.001
HC (cm)	95.11±8.33	90.34±7.34	P<0.01
WHR	0.9±0.03	0.8±0.02	P<0.001

Table 2: Body composition parameters

Parameters	IASDN(n=50)	ASDN(n=50)	P value
BMI (kg/m ²)	20.22±2.67	20.56±3.05	P<0.05
Fat (kg)	8.11±2.22	7.12±3.37	P<0.05
LBM (kg)	60.1±7.58	53.21±9.15	P<0.01
TBW (lit)	41.1±3.53	39.13±5.00	P<0.05

Discussion

The Bodystat Quadscan 4000 was used in the research that was described earlier in order to investigate the effect that the amount of time spent sleeping has on an individual's overall body composition. This study provides evidence that not getting enough sleep for an adequate amount of time can lead to higher body weight and increased fat gain in young adults. The research demonstrated that there are statistically significant differences in

anthropometric as well as compositional aspects of the body. According to the results of our research, the group that did not get an adequate amount of sleep had higher levels of weight, WC, HC, and WHR. Both body mass index (BMI) and total body fat measured in kilogram's were found to be higher in the IASDN group ($P = 0.020$). Our findings have been confirmed by research carried out in Korea and referred to as the National Health and

Nutrition Examination Surveys (KNHANES). They found that a shorter amount of time spent sleeping was inversely associated with body mass index, waist circumference, waist to hip ratio, and body fat percentage, while it was positively associated with skeletal muscle index. [10] It was observed that shorter periods of sleep were associated with higher BMIs, and vice versa. [8] Additional research has provided evidence to support the hypothesis that the total amount of time spent sleeping is a risk factor for obesity in both children and adults. [17-20]

On the other hand, a different study conducted on young adults in Gujarat found that they slept less ($p=0.00001$). [21] On the other hand, there is an interesting study that was conducted by Sadanand CD that found there was no correlation between sleep quality as measured by the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PQSI) and a variety of anthropometric parameters. [22] That insufficient sleep causes changes in the levels of a number of hormones is one of the plausible mechanisms that can be used to explain the connection between short sleep duration and obesity. A change in the regulation of orexin neurons and the hormones that regulate appetite could result in a change in food intake.

It has been demonstrated that cutting back on sleep causes an increase in the levels of the hormone ghrelin, while at the same time the levels of leptin, which is a hormone that causes satiety, go down. The levels of ghrelin over a period of 24 hours were measured by Spiegel *et al.* in relation to meals and the amount of time spent sleeping. They discovered that sleep can reduce the amount of ghrelin that is secreted into the bloodstream. Both the Positives and the Negatives of the Study The use of objective measures of obesity, as well as the participation of young adults, were both strengths of this particular study. The study has the drawback of having a relatively small sample size. There was no gender-specific statistical analysis carried out on

either group. The length of sleep was rated on a subjective scale. The PQSI scale is an improved instrument for determining the level of sleep quality experienced by the participants. It is possible that a study with a large number of participants would produce more accurate results. It is also important to measure the levels of ghrelin and leptin in the serum.

Conclusion

According to the findings of our study, being overweight is linked to not getting enough sleep. We suggest getting adequate amounts of sleep, in addition to high-quality sleep.

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